

Written in the Stars – Bird's Eye View on the Divine Equations of Everything – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

This paper will present with little to no explanation in words the entire mathematical framework of the 8-theory. It meant for researchers to have the equations in a concise paper as the thesis of the theory reached 80 pages, and the equations are spread along the entire range. The paper is than meant for those already familiar with the theory and its scope.

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{L}}{\partial \mathbf{s}} - \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \frac{\partial \mathbf{L}}{\partial \mathbf{s}'} = \mathbf{0} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.1)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (2.2)$$

Spin representation of the main equation (2)

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V \rightarrow \left[2N(\cdot) + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.3)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)